

ON THE LINEAR AND NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF THICK SYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The cylindrical bending of a thick symmetric cross-ply laminated plate subjected to an uniform transverse load is evaluated via the classical laminated plate theory, the Mindlin plate theory, the modified Mindlin plate theory, the linear thick plate theory and the non-linear thick plate theory, respectively. It is found that even the shear deformation is considered, the analysis via the thin plate theories all results in significant error. The analysis via the linear thick plate theory may also have 16% error, even in the range of small deflection. The errors decrease rapidly as the span to thickness ratio is increased.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the laminated anisotropic composites have been used considerably as structural elements of space vehicles, shipbuilding, automobiles and pressure vessels. This arises from the fact that, by taking advantage of its anisotropic material properties and light weight with high strength, the material can be used very efficiently.

It is a common practice to employ the linear classical laminated plate theory in the analysis of laminated composite plates when the deflection of the plate is small. Otherwise, the nonlinear theories such as Von Karmam's and Berger's large deflection theories are used [1-7]. Recently, Sun and co-workers [6-7] analyzed the cylindrical bending of several asymmetric composite laminates. Lee et. al. [8-9] investigated the cylindrical bending of the cross-ply and the symmetric angle-ply laminated plates. It was shown that the linear classical laminated plate theory may be not adequate for the analysis for several asymmetric composite laminates and symmetric angle-ply laminates with large stacking angle even in small deflection range. It was also observed that the temperature variation, thickness and boundary conditions have great influence on the accuracy of the linear and nonlinear analysis of the plate. Recently, Whitney [10-11] examined the cylindrical bending of a thick laminate plate. It was showed numerically that the effect of transverse normal stress on maximum deflection is small.

In this paper, we extend the previous studies and examine the cylindrical bending of a thick symmetric cross-ply laminated plate subjected to an uniform transverse load via the classical

laminated plate theory, the Mindlin plate theory, the modified Mindlin plate theory [12], the linear thick plate theory and the non-linear thick plate theory, respectively. The influence of the span to thickness ratio and the stacking sequence on the errors of the analysis is examined.

ANALYSIS

Consider a rectangular symmetric cross-ply thick laminated composite plate subjected to uniform lateral load q_0 . The plate is of length $2a$ in the x direction, infinite length in the y direction and thickness h in the z direction. The origin of the coordinate system is chosen to coincide with the center of the midplane of the undeformed plate. The plate is pinned-pinned supported at both sides of infinite length. Each layer has the same thickness and elastic properties.

For a cylindrical bending type problem, we assume that the displacement fields $u(x)$, $v(x)$ and $w(x)$ are independent of the y -axis. Base on the thick plate theory, the displacement fields of the system are

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z) &= u_0(x) + z\psi_x(x) \\ v(x, z) &= v_0(x) + z\psi_y(x) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$w(x) = \frac{3}{2h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} w_0(x) \left[1 - 4\left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2 \right] dz$$

where u_0 , v_0 and w_0 are the displacements of the middle plane in the x , y and z directions, respectively. ψ_x and ψ_y are the angles of rotation due to bending of the xz and yz planes, respectively.

Base on the Von Karman's large deformation theory, the strain-displacement relation are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_{0,x} \\ v_{0,x} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} w_{,xx}^2 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{x,x} \\ \psi_{y,x} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_y \\ \psi_x + w_{,x} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

where a comma denotes partial differentiation of the principle symbol with respect to the subscript. Following the notations used by Whitney [11], the stress-strain and the strain-stress relations in material principle coordinates are

$$\sigma_i = c_{ij} \epsilon_j, \quad \epsilon_i = s_{ij} \sigma_j \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 6 \tag{4}$$

and in structural principle coordinates are

$$\sigma_I = c'_{ij} \epsilon_J, \quad \epsilon_I = s'_{ij} \sigma_J \quad I, J = x, y, z, xy, xz, yz \tag{5}$$

consequently,

$$\sigma_I = (c'_{ik} - \frac{c'_{i3}c'_{k3}}{c'_{33}}) \epsilon_K + \frac{c'_{i3}}{c'_{33}} \sigma_z \quad (I, K = x, y, z), \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 6) \quad (6)$$

Upon substituting the stress-strain and the strain-displacement relations and the normal stress σ_z shown by Whitney [11]

$$\sigma_z = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[3 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \right] \left(\frac{z}{h} \right) q_0 + q_0 \right\} \quad (7)$$

into the resultant forces, moments and shears defined as:

$$N_I = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} \sigma_I dz \quad (8)$$

$$M_I = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} \sigma_I z dz \quad (9)$$

$$(Q_x, Q_y) = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}) dz \quad (10)$$

where t_k is the thickness of the k th ply, one has

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_I \\ M_I \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} A_{ij} & 0 \\ 0 & D_{ij} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_J \\ \kappa_J \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} L_1 q_0 \\ J_1 q_0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{x,x} \\ \psi_{y,x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$(A_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} (C'_{ij})_k (1, z^2) dz \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (13)$$

$$L_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} \frac{C'_{i3}}{C'_{33}} dz \quad (14)$$

$$J_1 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{t_{k-1}}^{t_k} \frac{C'_{i3}}{C'_{33}} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right) [3 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2] dz, \quad (15)$$

and

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_{55} & F_{45} \\ F_{45} & F_{44} \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_x + w_{,x} \\ \psi_y \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where

$$F_{44} = \frac{R_{55}}{R_{44}R_{55} - R_{45}^2}, \quad F_{55} = \frac{R_{44}}{R_{44}R_{55} - R_{45}^2}, \quad F_{45} = \frac{-R_{45}}{R_{44}R_{55} - R_{45}^2} \quad (17)$$

and

$$R_{ij} = \frac{9}{4h^2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} S_{ij} \left[1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \right]^2 dz \quad (i, j = 4, 5) \quad (18)$$

After substituting Eqns (11-18) into the following equilibrium differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial X} - Q_x &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial X} - Q_y &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_x}{\partial X} + q_0 + N_x \psi_{x,x} + N_{xy} (\psi_{x,x} + \psi_{y,x}) = 0$$

they become

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} \psi_{x,xx} - F_{55} \psi_x - F_{55} W_{,x} &= 0 \\ D_{66} \psi_{y,xx} - F_{44} \psi_y &= 0 \\ (N_x + F_{55}) \psi_{x,x} + N_{xy} \psi_{y,x} + F_{55} W_{,xx} + q_0 &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) are nonlinear equations. Together with the associated boundary conditions, they should be solved numerically.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, the composite considered is a graphite/epoxy AS/3501 with the material properties given as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 140 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \quad E_2 = 9.7 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \quad E_3 = 9.7 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \quad G_{12} = 4.8 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \\ G_{13} &= 4.3 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \quad G_{23} = 2.2 \text{KN} / \text{mm}^2, \quad \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.5. \end{aligned}$$

The thickness of each ply is taken to be the same and is 0.127 mm. The applied transverse load is adjusted such that the maximum out of plane deflection evaluated via the nonlinear thick plate theory is 1/10 of the total thickness of the plate.

In Table 1, the errors of the analysis for the composites with twenty two different stacking sequences are tabulated. Here, the errors are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{error1} &= \left| \frac{W_{\max 2} - W_{NL_{\max}}}{W_{NL_{\max}}} \right| \times 100\%, \quad \text{error2} = \left| \frac{W_{\max 1} - W_{NL_{\max}}}{W_{NL_{\max}}} \right| \times 100\%, \\ \text{error3} &= \left| \frac{W_{M_{\text{mindlin}}} - W_{NL_{\max}}}{W_{NL_{\max}}} \right| \times 100\%, \quad \text{error4} = \left| \frac{W_{CLPT} - W_{NL_{\max}}}{W_{NL_{\max}}} \right| \times 100\% \end{aligned}$$

- where W_{NL_max} : the maximum out of plane deflection evaluated via the nonlinear thick plate theory,
 W_{max2} : the maximum out of plane deflection evaluated via the linear thick plate theory, neglecting the in-plane force.
 W_{max1} : the maximum out of plane deflection evaluated via the modified Mindlin plate theory by Whitney [10].
 $W_{Mindlin}$: the maximum out of plane deflection evaluated via the Mindlin plate theory.
 W_{CLPT} : the maximum deflection evaluated via the classical laminated plate theory.

It can be found that even the shear deformation is considered, the analysis via the thin plate theories all results in significant error. The analysis via the linear thick plate theory may also have 16% error, even in the range of small deflection.

In Figure 1, the influence of the span to thickness ratio (L/H) on the errors of the analysis of the laminated composite plates is shown. It is observed that the errors decrease rapidly as the span to thickness ratio is increased.

CONCLUSION

It is a common and justified practice to employ the linear theory in the analysis of isotropic plates when the deflection of the plate is small. However, from the results revealed from the present analysis and those given by Sun et. al. and Lee et. al., it suggested that for certain kind of laminated composites, the nonlinear theory may be required in the analysis even when the deflection of the plate is small. The boundary conditions, stacking sequence and the span to thickness ratio will have significant influence on the accuracy of the analysis.

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Table 1: The errors of the analysis for pinned-pinned supported symmetric cross-ply laminated plates with 57 layers and the span to thickness ratio, L/H = 5.

N=57, H=7.239mm , L/H=5 , WNL _{CEN} / H = 1 / 10, A=90° pinned-pinned supported plates				
STACKING SEQUENCE	error1(%)	error2(%)	error3(%)	error4(%)
[A/AAAAAAAAAAAAA]2s	7.2	29.0	35.7	38.5
[0/AAAAAAAAAAAAA]2s	7.5	29.6	35.9	38.8
[0/000000A]4s	7.8	31.2	36.2	39.2
[A/000000A]4s	8.2	31.7	36.4	39.5
[0/A0A0A0A0A0A0A0]2s	10.2	33.1	36.6	40.5
[A/A0A0A0A0A0A0A0]2s	10.7	33.3	36.7	40.6
[0/A00000AA000000A]2s	10.9	33.4	36.8	40.8
[A/A00000AA000000A]2s	11.5	33.5	37.0	40.8
[0/A0A0A000000000]2s	11.5	33.7	37.0	40.9
[A/A0A0A000000000]2s	12.2	33.8	37.1	40.9
[A/00000AA]4s	12.7	34.3	37.4	41.3
[0/00000AA]4s	12.7	34.4	37.4	41.4
[0/0000AAA]4s	12.9	34.6	37.5	41.5
[A/0000AAA]4s	13.1	34.8	37.6	41.6
[0/A00A00AA00A00A]2s	13.2	34.9	37.6	41.5
[A/A00A00AA00A00A]2s	13.5	35.0	37.7	41.6
[0/0AA00AA]4s	13.8	35.3	37.8	41.9
[A/0AA00AA]4s	14.1	35.6	37.9	41.9
[0/AA000AA]4s	14.4	35.8	38.0	42.3
[A/AA000AA]4s	15.0	35.9	38.2	42.5
[A/AAAAAAAAAAAA0000]2s	15.0	36.1	38.3	42.6
[0/AAAAAAAAAAAA0000]2s	15.1	36.2	38.3	42.7
[0/0AA0AAA]4s	15.4	36.4	38.4	43.2
[A/0AA0AAA]4s	15.5	36.4	38.5	43.3
[0/AAA0AAA]4s	15.8	37.3	38.8	43.7
[A/AAA0AAA]4s	16.1	37.6	38.8	43.9

Figure 1: The influence of the span to thickness ratio on the errors of the analysis for a pinned-pinned supported symmetric cross-ply laminated plate with 57 layers and stacking sequence $[90/90/90/0/90/90/90]_4s$.

